

How can standards facilitate the setting up and management of sustainable SMEs supply chains?

Issue Date: 16/02/2022

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 958352.

Our main findings

In the fragmented and continuously evolving supply chains supported by the TRICK project, the most relevant challenge is the **creation of common understanding**, using as much as possible existing standards, even if incomplete, in order to facilitate replication and diffusion of the projects results among SMEs.

In this context, the main objective of the first phase of the project was the **definition of the reference framework for the TRICK platform activities**: on one side the definition of the technical and semantic reference for information exchanges along the supply chains of TRICK; on the other side the preliminary study for managing effective and efficient PEF (Product Environmental Footprint) evaluations on the supported final products.

The necessary activities to reach the expected results evidenced some issues to be faced. Firstly, because of the emerging complexity of the six TRICK services¹ and the need for deepening their mechanisms, it was necessary to carry out a deep analysis on the services' scenarios. Secondly, the reference existing standards and specifications (UNECE UN/CEFACT², PEFCR, CEN CWA eBIZ³) are at a stage of draft or partial development or are not enough complete to cover sustainability aspects of the supply chains. Thirdly, the worldwide pandemic situation affected the working activities, reduced the possibility of physical meetings and made the alignment between the parallel ongoing activities a bit more complex.

The outcome of D1.4 – “Harmonized set of semantic standards, ontologies, nomenclatures” is **a framework based on UNECE methodology for transparent and sustainable supply chains**, on CEN CWA eBIZ specifications for data exchange, on PEF Category Rules (PEFCR) for apparel products and a number of other standards and nomenclatures to be used in the TRICK platform. Finally, original contribution from the TRICK project will complement such a framework.

New model of collaboration with Custom Agencies, semantic standards and specifications adoption and improvements and PEF standardization are the main topics that might receive an effective and relevant contribution from the TRICK project, as detailed in section 2 *Policy implications and Recommendations*.

Moreover, there might be an important contribution also on **policy recommendations about Traceability and transparency in the Fashion Industry**, thanks to the implementation of UNECE's guidelines in TRICK, with a focus on the **applicability of circularity** in textile and clothing (TC) sector.

¹ Secured Traceability and Preferential Certification of Origin (PCO), Circular manufacturing assessment, PEF and environmental footprint, Health protection assessment, Social and ethical protection assessment, A.I for Anti-counterfeiting

² <https://tfig.itcilo.org/contents/org-unece-with-uncefact.htm>

³ www.ebiz.enea.it

1 Introduction

The work carried out during the first phase of the project, focused mainly on semantic data model and on the preliminary phase of the PEF studies in TC sector, are summarized in the present document, with a section on its main contribution to policies, that could be effective when supported by the design, development and validation activities of the next project's phases.

An iterative process was adopted, first to collect information, then to refine the defined TRICK services' scenarios and classify data and documents that has to be exchanged.

1.1 The semantic data model and the role of standards

1.1.1 Reference Standards and specifications

The analysis of the state of the art in the field of data sharing models and interoperability⁴, the key element for enabling data exchange between the systems, had a focus on the existing semantic and transactional standards. It was soon clear that, for the purpose of TRICK, in order to facilitate the adoption within SME, the possibility to exploit the existence of a vertical⁵ standardized specification in the domain of the pilots would be a great opportunity.

Nevertheless, the situation is not totally satisfying such expectations because for the Textile Clothing and Footwear domain there are only two exploitable alternatives: on one hand a vertical specification (**CEN CWA eBIZ**), that covers the process from raw material up to the finished product and supports the subcontracting relationships with some limitations in terms of support for sustainability; on the other hand a specialisation of a horizontal standard (**UNECE UN/CEFACT**) for the sectorial supply chains, that has been improved to support the traceability and sustainability issues of the fashion industry (but presently the data specifications have not been published).

For the **Food** sector there is not a vertical dedicated standard to support the supply chain; on the contrary, there is a number of implementations of the **GS1 EANCOM** specifications due to the capacity of the Large Retail Organizations to impose this standard that is familiar to their systems, but not foreseen for sustainability and traceability.

PEFCRs (Product Environmental Footprint Category Rules), the specifications of the PEF general guidance for a specific domain, include consistent and specific set of rules to calculate the relevant environmental information of products belonging to a product category. Nevertheless, at the time of writing, the final PEFCRs for the TC sector but are very limited, available only for T-shirts and leather and only a draft **PEFCR on Apparel and Footwear** has been published in July 2021, but it still is incomplete and not finalized.

⁴ Two definitions of interoperability: “The ability of a system or a product to work with other systems or products without special effort on the part of the customer” (whatis.com). “The ability of two or more systems or components to exchange information and to use the information that has been exchanged” (Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers. IEEE Standard Computer Dictionary: A Compilation of IEEE Standard Computer Glossaries. New York, NY: 1990)

⁵ A 'Vertical' standard is tailored for a specific domain, ready to use, easier to implement and clearly understood by the stakeholders without the needs for a domain specific implementation guide

1.1.2 Organizational models and data flows for TRICK’s circular supply chains: the UNECE methodology applied to TRICK

The outcome of UNECE project’s activities on “Enhancing Traceability and Transparency for Sustainable Value Chains in the Garment and Footwear Sector”⁶ has been chosen as the main reference that TRICK has assumed to model the traceability data collection along the TC and Food supply chains, enabling industries to enhance its management and to adopt more sustainable production and consumption patterns, favoring the reuse and recycling of products, identifying and managing labour, human rights violations and environmental impacts, fighting counterfeits. This choice is thought to assure the interoperability between the involved systems and achieve data sharing along the whole supply chain, enhancing transparency and traceability. A representative of this project has been invited to TRICK Executive Advisory Board and ENEA, the partner in charge of these activities, is involved in both projects.

The UNECE methodology is applied to both TC and Food sectors, starting from the identification of the most important claims that have to be supported by the project (see Table 1 for an extract from D1.4 Claims table).

Table 1: Examples of Claims supported by TRICK in TC scenario

Traceable asset	Claimed state	Objective	Macro category	Main claim target
Final product or Lot of Fabric/ Yarn	Minimum two main manufacturing activities were done in Europe	Define the right duty category and have access to lower preferential duties when exporting	Origin	Customs
Final product or Lot of Fabric/Yarn/Fibre	This is made of XYZ % of reused fibre	Real circularity ‘embedded’ in the product	Circularity	Final user, Retail organisation
Secondary raw material (Fibre)	This fibre is suitable for a XYZ usage / treatment (no risks, workability)	Encourage appropriate reuse of materials and products	Circularity	Industry customer
Final product	The PEF impacts of this product are x, y, z, etc..	Demonstrate a low environmental impact though measurable and comparable indicators	Environmental Sustainability	Final user, Industry customer, Retail organisation

The overall idea is to collect data exchanged mainly in the “usual businesses” between the actors of the TRICK supply chain in a standard format, store them or their footprints into the Blockchain, in order to assure their consistency and authenticity, and then process them being able to reconcile information along the whole supply chain.

The role of the blockchain in this approach is assuring integrity, authenticity, non-repudiation and proof of existence of these evidences so that, in case of disputation of authority check, it is proven the existence and integrity and coherence of the collected information.

1.1.3 TRICK services scenarios analysis and data model

The first step to carry out the definition of TRICK platform data model was the identification of the data flows and the information necessary to support TRICK’s services. The main objectives, the affected pilots (TC/Food), the actors and roles are identified for each of the six services of TRICK. Then, the “as is” service’s scenario is detailed, with its steps and peculiarity, followed by the description of the “to be” scenario, which identifies the role and the steps that

⁶ <https://unece.org/trade/traceability-sustainable-garment-and-footwear>

TRICK platform will carry out to support its users, depicted in a general diagram of the main activities of the service, when available.

Thanks to this preliminary analysis, it was possible to identify the managed and exchanged documents and data transactions in each scenario, which will be at the basis of the TRICK platform data model, together with a preliminary list of new and relevant concepts for the ontology and a list of certificates, labels, standard and regulations relevant for each service.

1.1.4 PEF and PEFCRs

A preliminary definition of operative guidelines for the execution of the PEF studies of the categories of products of the TRICK TC pilots had been provided, together with a matrix with the data needed to perform a PEF study on the products objects of the pilots. Part of the relevant effort was spent in the creation of a common understanding between the participants, thanks to a very short crash course about PEF method and PEFCRs, and further interactions with end users involved in the pilots. Moreover, the analysis of the existing PEFCR specifications for apparel and footwear was already performed in these first months of the project although they are still under discussion and not finalized.

A critical point that has been identified is the flows of information along the supply chain to reuse as much as possible the same data from the suppliers (a 'modular' approach); presently the validation approach of PEF seems to poorly allow this TRICK approach.

The efforts required to decide how to overcome the gaps and this work will be the basis for the contribution of the project to the fora active for collecting comments and suggestions.

2 Policy implications and Recommendations

The TRICK project, with its relevant consortium, will play an important role in the framework of designing and characterizing the TC supply chains of the future. Its objectives in terms of supporting the transition from linear to circular, enhancing the transparency of the business processes and the traceability of the products, providing secured and faithfulness data also to support companies in their relationships with regulatory entities, like Custom Agencies, are the keys to a new approach to products and data managements within TC sector.

The work carried out in the first phase of the project led to relevant inputs for policy makers and stakeholders, as it has approached the following topics:

Policy recommendation about Traceability and transparency in the Fashion Industry

The guidelines of the UNECE project "Enhancing Traceability and Transparency for Sustainable Value Chains in the Garment and Footwear Sector" project⁷, and their related policies recommendations n.46⁸, has been chosen as the main reference that TRICK has assumed to model the traceability data collection along the TC supply chains. The implementation of such guidelines in TRICK and the suggestions and comments on its suitability for replication on different supply chains, such as the Food ones, will be reported to UNECE's expert group, with a focus on the applicability of circularity In TC sector.

⁷ <https://unece.org/trade/traceability-sustainable-garment-and-footwear>

⁸ "Recommendation n.46: Enhancing Traceability and Transparency for Sustainable Value Chains in the Garment and Footwear Sector", UNECE, April 2021; ECE/TRADE/CEFAT/2021/10

New model of collaboration with Custom Agencies

The model of collaboration with the Italian Custom agency, analyzed and depicted in the PCO service analysis with the aim of facilitating and speeding-up the processes between trusted supply chain and customs agencies, will be a pilot reported to the European level through the common tables of discussion between the national agencies and the DG TAXUD. A new collaborative model to support the PCO management for companies is going to be defined, facing issues like interoperability between TRICK platform and Customs systems and use of the blockchain to ensure transparency of the supply chains processes and faithfulness of information, and could be proposed as reference model for European Customs Agencies.

Semantic standards and specifications adoption and improvements

One of the objectives of TRICK project is to improve digitalization of business process in TC and Food supply chains, through the adoption and use of reference standard. As already explained, a specific standard that could cover all the TRICK needs doesn't exist, but there are some standards and specification that could cover peculiar aspects, even if missing other ones. For example, regarding the eBIZ specifications for inter-company data exchange, a line of improvement and extension has been identified in order to support traceability and circularity in the fashion industry. The final results might be a contribution to the eBIZ development to be presented to EURATEX (that is managing the specifications) and in case to CEN, the European Committee for Standardization. Moreover, a contribution to the UN/CEFACT outcomes is under experimentation.

PEF standardization

Regarding the work of standardization for applying PEF in the TC sector, being managed by a team led by SAC (Sustainable Apparel Coalition⁹) on behalf of the European Commission, we expect to be able to contribute to the draft PEFCR for textile products on two aspects:

- applicability of their contents, with comments and concrete use cases
- development and completion of the Category Rules, presenting meaningful input from the PEF service implementation and pilots' activities and results.

⁹ <https://apparelcoalition.org/>